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GLIMPSES ON VALIDATION OF ASSAY METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF ITRACONAZOLE IN ITRACONAZOLE TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY UV-SPECTROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, quick, and affordable UV spectrophotometric technique is created and proven to be effective for figuring out the dosages of itraconazole in tablets and bulk. The drug is soluble in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, and dimethyl formamide. Itraconazole in tablet form can be measured simply, rapidly, and economically with the UV method. UV spectroscopic analysis is conducted at an absorption maximum of 262 nm using methanol as a solvent. In accordance with ICH criteria, the suggested approach was verified for linearity, precision, accuracy, sensitivity, and robustness. This review is really comprehensive, and the procedure for measuring itraconazole is a simple and accurate method.

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INTRODUCTION

Itraconazole is known chemically as 2-butan-2-yl-4-[4-[4-[4-[(2R,4S)-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(1,2,4-triazol-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl] methoxy] phenyl] piperazin-1-yl] phenyl]-1,2,4-triazol-3-one. Itraconazole is an official drug in the United States Pharmacopoeia, European Pharmacopoeia, and British Pharmacopoeia. A broad-spectrum antifungal derived from synthetic triazole agent, it is effective against a variety of topical and systemic fungal infections orally. Itraconazole tablets are used to treat fungal infections, such as aspergillosis (fungal infection in the lungs), blastomycosis (Gilchrist's disease), or histoplasmosis (Darling's disease), and are advised for the treatment and prevention of the spread of yeast infections of the mouth, throat, or oesophagus (tube that connects the throat to the stomach). Before receiving a bone marrow transplant, patients who are prone to yeast infections are treated with this medication during chemotherapy or radiation therapy. The affinity of itraconazole for mammalian P450s 14 α -demethylase is lower. The effect is fungistatic, but may be fungicidal at higher concentrations. (Figure. 1)^[3]

It appears as a white crystalline powder, sparingly soluble in water and very soluble in alcohol. Itraconazole inhibits the enzyme CYP P450 14 α -demethylase in fungal infection [4]. Itraconazole is mainly a broad spectrum bacteriostatic antifungal category. However, it can have a dose-dependent fungicidal effect against some microorganisms, especially candida, candidiasis, aspergillosis, and cryptococcosis. This is all the virus is the leading cause of opportunistic fungal infections globally, causing everything from superficial mucosal infections to potentially fatal systemic infections. Cutaneous Candidiasis, also known as Skin Candidiasis, is a fungal infection of the skin caused by Candida fungus. According to an epidemiological survey in India, Candida non-albicans, particularly C. tropicalis, were responsible for 67-90% of nosocomial candidemia infections. In recent decades, there have been numerous instances of Candida infections in India. There are some people who are allergic to azoles and so many individuals who are allergic to other azole drugs may also be allergic to itraconazole. This means that some azole drugs can have side effects. Some azole medications can interfere with estrogen production during pregnancy and affect the outcome of the pregnancy [5].

Itraconazole is a weakly basic class II (low solubility/high permeability) medicine in the Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS). Its dissolution is pH-dependent (pKa value: 3.7), indicating that it usually needs an acidic stomach environment to dissolve the drug adequately and absorb it efficiently. Itraconazole is an antifungal prescribed medicine approved by the U.S. Food And Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of certain fungal infections such as aspergillosis, Blastomycosis, Histoplasmosis.[2].

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Itraconazole.

Table 1: Drug profile of itraconazole.

Generic Name	Itraconazole
Brand Name	Sporanox, Onmel.
IUPAC Name	2-butan-2-yl-4-[4-[4-[4-[(2R,4S)-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(1,2,4-triazol-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl] methoxy] phenyl] piperazin-1-yl] phenyl]-1,2,4-triazol-3-one
Chemical formula	C ₃₅ H ₃₈ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₄
Molar Mass	705.6 g.mol
Synonyms	Sporanox, Onmel, Tosura
Melting point	168-170 °C
Solubility	Insoluble in Water and soluble in dilute acidic solutions
Protein binding	99.8%
Elimination half life	34 to 40 hrs

HPLC Method:

A literature review revealed several HPLC methods for the quantitative determination of itraconazole in pharmaceutical formulations using variations in mobile phase, column, and detector. There are various HPLC methods for FLC in the official pharmacopoeia for individual studies, and several LC-MS/MS methods have been used to determine FLC in human plasma. Therefore, an attempt was made to develop a simple, efficient and selective RP-HPLC method for the intracellular measurement of FLC concentration and use it in azole-resistant *C. albicans* [6].

Principle:

HPLC is a separation technique. A small amount of liquid sample (3 to 5 microns (μm) in diameter, called the stationary phase) is injected into a tube and individual portions of the sample are separated. The bottom of the tube fills up. The liquid (solid phase) is injected into a tube (column) and enters the pressurized column at high pressure delivered by a pump. These components are separated by columnar packing, which involves various chemical and/or physical interactions between the molecules and the packing particles [7]. At the outlet of the pipe (valve), this ratio is detected by a flow device (detector) that measures its value. The output of this detector is called "HPLC". In theory, LC and HPLC work similarly, but HPLC excels in speed, efficiency, sensitivity, and ease of operation. Although HPLC retains much of its analytical reliability, simple liquid chromatography principles are used for primary purposes. As shown in the schematic diagram above, an HPLC instrument consists of a solvent reservoir, a pump, an injector, a column, a detector, an integrator or absorber, and a display system. The main part of the system is the separation column [7,8].

UV spectroscopy:

Ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy is a physical optical spectroscopy technique that uses light in the visible, ultraviolet, and infrared ranges and is based on the Beer-Lambert law, which states that the absorbance of a solution is directly proportional to its concentration. Mass absorption modes and path lengths in solution. Therefore, if the path length is constant, it can be used to determine the concentration of the adsorbent in the solution. Because of the need to know the rate of change in absorption and concentration, UV-VIS spectroscopy has been used continuously for the past 37 years and has become one of the most important analytical techniques and revolutionary tools in modern laboratories. . Although other methods can be used in many applications, it does not compete with UV-VIS spectroscopy in terms of simplicity, versatility, accuracy, speed, and cost-effectiveness [6,9].

Principle of UV spectroscopy:

Molecules or ions absorb in the visible or ultraviolet region when radiation causes electronic transitions in their structure. Therefore, the absorption of light by the sample in the ultraviolet or visible region requires a change in the electronic state of the molecules in the sample. The energy provided by the light drives the electron into a higher energy, excited state, or anti-bonding orbital, from its ground state orbital. There are three types of Earth's orbit [10].

1. σ (Bonding) molecular
2. π (Bonding) molecular orbital
3. n (non-Bonding) atomic orbital.

Figure 2: Instrumentation of UV-Spectroscopy.

From the literature review, it was found that several gas chromatography [11,12], microbiological methods [13] and HPLC detection methods [28-16] have been performed on different formulations of itraconazole. There are methods to assess itraconazole alone or in combination with body fluids such as serum [17-19]. Combined UV spectrophotometry has been reported to measure itraconazole in eye drops or in combination. However, no method has been found to estimate itraconazole in tablet doses using UV spectroscopy. This shows that until now there is no UV method for the estimation and determination of itraconazole in tablet dosage form [20].

METHOD DEVELOPMENTS:

Instruments:

The Jasco (UV 550) Double Beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer 1700 Ultra is an ideal partner. Quartz cell, bath sonicator, and civilian balance capable of 1 cm optical path length and 1 nm spectral bandwidth. An Equiptronics melting point device was used [21].

Determination of λ max (100 PPM):

100 mg of itraconazole was dissolved in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Pour the tube into a 10 ml 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolve and label. This solution was scanned from 200 to 400 nm to determine the absorption maxima [21].

Selection of detection Wavelength:

To determine the λ peak of itraconazole, a solution of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ itraconazole in CH_3OH was prepared and scanned at a UV wavelength between 200 and 400 nm. When using a solvent ratio of methanol to water (50:50), the maximum UV λ_{max} was obtained at 262 nm [8].

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:

An exact weight of 10 mg of itraconazole was dissolved in 10 mg of methanol: water (50:50) in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Prepare a stock solution of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ itraconazole in the above solution by sonication. A solution of methanol: water (50:50) contains a concentration between 20 and 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ [23].

Figure 3: UV Visible Spectra of Itraconazole.

Preparation of Calibration curve:

Appropriate dilutions were prepared from the itraconazole stock solution prepared above to obtain final concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and the λ_{max} absorbance at 260 nm was measured. The average value of these five sets, the standard calibration curve, and the calibration curve are plotted. Eye doses are used with concentrations from 20 to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Linearity was calculated using the least squares regression method. Itraconazole calibration data is shown in Table 1. Figure 2 shows the calibration curve of itraconazole [24].

VALIDATION OF METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

The proposed method was developed in 1996 based on ICH guidelines with linearity, accuracy, precision and robustness.

Linearity and Range:

Different amounts of itraconazole were extracted from 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 ml of stock solution using methanol:water solution (50:50) in 10 ml and 20 concentrations of $\sim 100 \mu\text{g}$. / accepted. Absorbance at 260 nm of each concentration was recorded after each milliliter and the calibration graph of absorbance against each concentration was plotted. The beer rule was followed in the range of 20–100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ [25].

Precision:

A detailed study was conducted to confirm the reproducibility of this method. Reproducibility is determined by repeating the sample six times at the same concentration and measuring absorbance. A detailed study at home was done by analyzing the drug solution prepared three times a day (8-hour sampling). The same procedure was repeated on three different days to measure daily accuracy. The results are reported as %RSD [21].

Accuracy:

To ensure the accuracy of the method, three sample solutions were prepared at a concentration of 80, 100 and 120%, each sample solution containing an amount of active drug and a volumetric solution of 100 ml of analytical grade. Recovery tests are done by dilution in flasks. Measure the absorbance at 252 nm [2].

Table 2: Accuracy study (Spectrophotometric method).

Accuracy (%)	Quantity weighed (mg)	Quantity found (mg)	Recovery (96-102%)
60	0.6	0.72	96.82
80	0.8	0.96	98.02
100	10	1.02	99.89

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) [26,27]:

LOD is the lowest detectable amount of analyte in a sample. LOQ is the lowest amount of an analyte in a sample that can be calculated with quantitative accuracy and precision. LOD and LOQ are calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma/S,$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma/S.$$

Where,

σ is the standard deviation of the Y intercept of the calibration curve and S is the slope of the regression equation. The linearity equation was found to be $y = 0.0017x + 0.0547$.

The LOD and LOQ values were found to be 6.563741 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 19.89012 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

Robustness:

To determine the reliability of the method analysis was carried out using a standard at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at two different wavelengths and at room temperature, and the corresponding absorbance was measured [23].

Repeatability

A concentration of 240 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared from a stock solution of itraconazole and its absorbance was measured against 0.1 N hydrochloride at a wavelength of 239 nm. standard deviation and relative deviation were calculated [14].

Reproducibility

The 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ solution was prepared separately from the itraconazole stock solution and analyzed at 239 nm by the analyzer (analyte 1). The same solution was prepared by another analyst and the values obtained were evaluated using a t-test to ensure reproducibility [29,30].

CONCLUSION

A stable UV- Visible Spectroscopic method was investigated for desidustst measurements. The main advantages of this method are significant cost reduction, ease of use, ease of operation and short implementation time. All these features are important when working, especially when analyzing a large number of samples. Verification tests show that this procedural approach has a wide calibration concentration range, sufficient accuracy and precision, and sensitivity to be reliable in practice. Tests are performed to confirm the identity, standard, quality, and purity of standard APIs through UV spectra, solubility studies, and melting point measurements. The developed method was validated for suitability, specificity, accuracy, precision, linearity and robustness.

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